

HABITAT ACCESSIBILITY IN THE DESIGN OF NATURE-INCLUSIVE VOID FEATURES IN MARINE STRUCTURES

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Highlight: Void features increase the volume of interstitial space and their accessibility to a wider range of accessing diameters.

Keywords: Complexity; digital; habitat; modelling; refugia

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ABSTRACT

Nature-inclusive design aims to enhance the ecological performance of human-made marine structures with positive habitat features, like internal void spaces. Currently, interstitial space metrics are inadequate in quantifying the volume of void spaces whilst considering their geometric properties. We propose a new analytical method to inform nature-inclusive design called accessible space analysis, and two new accessibility metrics to be quantified from digital habitat models: Accessible Volume (AV) and Accessible Refuge Volume (ARV). We calculated AV and ARV with a numerical modelling program, from digital models of artificial habitats, comparing them to a conventional metric: total interstitial volume (V_{int}). ARV was calculated considering access classes with a minimum to maximum size ratio of 1:5, to assess refugia provision for fishes from predation. Our experiment included four ordered structural layouts, with known geometric properties, and a nature-inclusive design scenario, comparing two designs of hypothetical berm structures, one with a conventional graded rock design and a second with Reef cubes®, incorporating void features. The visualization of accessible space and accessibility metrics distinguished the ordered layouts, for which V_{int} remained constant. When comparing the berm designs, both the conventional V_{int} and accessibility metrics were greater in the Reef cube® design. V_{int} was 66% higher, mean difference of AV was 369% higher and mean difference of ARV 172% higher across 10 access classes. The results indicate that the integrated void features increased the availability of accessible space and refugia, especially for accessing diameters below the maximum void entry diameter in the Reef cube® units, suggesting that accessible space positively describes void geometry on a per unit design basis in such combined structures. Accessible space analysis provides a robust methodology for generating size-sensitive information from structured habitats, capable of differentiating marine structural designs based on functional habitat accessibility and providing expansive insight to complement existing methods.

1 INTRODUCTION

A growing ecological awareness for a more sustainable future is driving the adoption of tools and solutions aimed at mitigating human impact on marine environments and returning nature to modified areas (Airoldi et al., 2021). Among these, a new way of thinking around marine infrastructure is gaining traction, promoting nature positive approaches that integrate engineering efficiency with ecological performance for the benefit of both humans and nature (O'Shaughnessy et al., 2020; Pardo et al., 2023; Schoonees et al., 2019). In this context, there is a growing use of structures that act as *de-facto* artificial reefs (as per (London Convention and Protocol/ UNEP, 2009)), either as a primary or secondary objective (e.g. scour protection structures or low-crested coastal defence structures (Degraer et al., 2020; Moschella et al., 2005)). Nature-inclusive design can be applied to these

structures to better integrate them with marine ecosystems, through the intentional incorporation of science-backed habitat features (British Standards Institution, 2025).

Artificial reef research is a rich resource for informing the selection of nature-inclusive design features. Modern artificial reef design enhances external (e.g. rugosity) and internal (interstitial space) complexity to provide refuges for fish communities (Charbonnel, 2002; Pondella et al., 2022), which are often the primary ecological target of these structures (Blount et al., 2021). The emphasis on refuge creation is supported by evidence showing that the provision of suitable refugia is a key factor in increasing fish abundance, size, and species richness (Sherman et al., 2002). The pre-immersion characterization of an artificial reef's structural complexity, supported by modern computational power, photogrammetry and 3D Computer Aided Design (CAD) technology, is now a valuable tool for predicting its ecological efficiency and guiding reef design. This shift moves away from the empirical approaches of the past toward a more standardized methodology (Riera et al., 2024), building on the well-documented influence of complexity in structuring biotic assemblages (Kovalenko et al., 2012).

While much research has focused on the effects of external complexity (Loke and Chisholm, 2022), the role of internal complexity – specifically its size, abundance, diversity, scale, or arrangement (Tokeshi and Arakaki, 2012) – on reef fish remains largely unexplored, with only a few promising insights emerging (Taira et al., 2024). This knowledge gap is primarily due to the lack of efficient methodologies for characterizing interstitial space, which is currently assessed through empirical approaches or simplified one-dimensional and two-dimensional metrics (Bartholomew et al., 2000; Charbonnel, 2002; Dibble et al., 1996). Interstitial spaces play a critical role in shaping community composition, biodiversity, secondary production, and species dynamics (Charbonnel, 2002; Hesterberg et al., 2017; Martin et al., 2012; Rouse et al., 2020; Toscano and Griffen, 2013; Williams, 1972). Yet current approaches for studying interstitial refuges in the context of species dynamics have been developed for specific predator-prey systems in small-scale reefs (Callaway, 2018), 2.5D substrates (Bertolini et al., 2018; Gregor and Anderson, 2016), or habitats formed by plant canopies and macrophytes (Bartholomew, 2012; Bartholomew et al., 2000). Hence, these methods may not be well-suited for the comprehensive characterization of marine infrastructure and its structural properties.

The growing demand for nature-inclusive structures capable of delivering high ecological performance necessitates the development and testing of metrics that can accurately characterize interstitial spaces within these structures (British Standards Institution, 2025). In this study, we demonstrate the applicability of a new approach to characterising interstitial space to assess internal complexity and refuge availability based on a key interstitial space condition: accessibility. *Accessibility* is a property of interstitial spaces within a structure, determined by whether an organism can physically enter and

move through the space solely due to its body size. We expect that appropriate metrics to quantify the availability of interstitial refugia based on their accessibility will improve our understanding of how internal complexity shapes the species dynamics of organisms inhabiting marine infrastructure (Bartholomew, 2012; Bartholomew et al., 2000; Bertolini et al., 2018; Hesterberg et al., 2017). By developing the conceptual framework to more accurately and comprehensively measure the interstitial refuges in complex structured habitats, we aim to offer further valuable approaches for the evidence-based nature-inclusive design of bespoke structures, strategically oriented toward specific ecological and functional goals.

To achieve this, we introduce the concept of accessible space, along with versatile quantitative metrics of it. To demonstrate a novel approach of accessible space analysis, we compare these metrics to the related, established, summary metric of interstitial space (Callaway, 2018; Taira et al., 2024), the Total Interstitial Volume (V_{int}), which serves here as a non-accessibility-based benchmark. We performed accessible space analysis on digital structured habitat models in two stages. Firstly, to four ordered simulated objects, each with identical expected V_{int} , to assess the ability of accessibility metrics to differentiate sub-unit spatial arrangements. Secondly, to a feasible real-world nature-inclusive design scenario, comparing two berm structures, to investigate the potential effect of void design features on refuge availability to a hypothetical fish community.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Interstitial space metrics

2.1.1 Total interstitial volume (V_{int})

Total interstitial volume is the total volume of interstitial space in a marine benthic habitat. The greater the interstitial volume, the higher the likelihood for fish to find shelter and hide from predators (Tsuchiya and Nishihira, 1985).

For complex hard substrates it is often calculated by subtracting the solid volume, measured either geometrically (Sadchatheeswaran et al., 2019a) or by water displacement (Van Dover and Trask, 2000), from the total space occupied by the structure.

V_{int} does not distinguish between interstitial spaces of different sizes within the same habitat, it is a quantification of the cumulative volume of all the individual spaces combined. A combination of many, small spaces, within a habitat could result in the same V_{int} as one single large space. V_{int} is therefore expected to poorly discriminate refuge availability across different interstitial space arrangements in habitats, especially considering the constraints imposed by species morphology and habitat preferences. Individual interstitial spaces have been shown to be a relevant factor for ecological

phenomena like prey survivorship (Hesterberg et al., 2017), so to bolster the informative capacity of V_{int} we introduce the new concept of accessible space, incorporating geometric constraints to interstitial spatial accessibility in analyses, to more adequately detect and quantify their feasible ecological function.

2.1.2 Accessible Space and Accessible Volume (AV)

Accessible space is defined here as interstitial space that a sphere can theoretically pass through considering access from an exterior environment and given its diameter (hereafter referred to as ‘accessing diameter’). We define the metric ‘Accessible Volume’ (AV) as the total volume of accessible space in a habitat. We propose a manner of notation for AV that incorporates the accessing diameter, of AV_{Diameter} . For example, the accessible volume for a sphere of diameter 30 mm could be noted as $AV_{30\text{mm}}$.

One can expect the magnitude of AV only ever to remain the same or decrease with increases in accessing diameter because a larger sphere is theoretically unable to access a larger volume of space within a network of interstitial space than a smaller one. A decay function of varying form can therefore be expected (as illustrated in figure 1).

Figure 1 An example decay function illustrating the inverse relationship between accessible volume and accessing diameter

2.1.3 Access classes and ARV

We propose an additional derivative metric called Accessible Refuge Volume (ARV) to further classify accessible space. ARV is to be calculated by quantifying AV within specific ranges of accessing diameters (‘access classes’). Access classes are a means of segmenting the continuous accessing

diameter variable into categorical groupings, which can be specified to relate to ecological functions of the habitat. Our intention with the creation of ARV is to provide additional structural insights relevant to marine ecology, such as the provision of refugia from predation.

Mathematically ARV for an access class can be calculated as the difference between the AV of the access class's minimum accessing diameter and the AV of the access class's maximum accessing diameter (see Figure 2).

$$ARV_{Min, Max} = AV_{Min} - AV_{Max}$$

Figure 2 An illustration of feasible lower and upper bounds of an ARV access class, permitting further informative classification of accessible space.

We propose the notation $ARV_{Min, Max}$, where the subscripts refer to the lower and upper bounds of the access class. For example, $ARV_{50, 70mm}$ represents the volume accessible to a 50 mm diameter sphere but not to one of 70 mm. To logically define the concept, ARV can be considered as the volume of interstitial space inaccessible to a sphere of diameter equal to the class maximum and accessible to a sphere of diameter equal to the class minimum.

In calculating ARV, spaces that are accessible to the access class's maximum diameter are removed from the final calculation.

2.2 Ordered layout modelling

To evaluate how effectively accessible space analysis characterises interstitial space across different spatial configurations, and to compare the accessibility metrics - AV and ARV - with the V_{Int} metric, we applied accessibility analysis to four composite artificial reef models, in ordered layouts. The artificial reef models were designed using Autodesk Fusion CAD software (Autodesk, 2025). Each model had

an identical total volume of 1 m³ and consisted of 64 “RC250” Reef cube[®] units arranged in a regular, ordered layout. Hereafter, these models are referred to as Ordered Layouts 1 through 4 (OL1 - OL4)

Reef cubes[®] are a cubic design, containing internal void spaces in the form of a central spherical chamber, connected to the exterior by six cylindrical passages - one in each face of the cube. The Reef cubes[®] selected in this study had an edge length of 250 mm. Four distinct internal void designs were developed, with 16 units of each design included in every model layout (Table 1). The four designs, labelled A through D, varied by increasing passage and chamber diameters, with design A having the smallest voids and design D having the largest. Passages ranged from 75 mm to 150 mm, and chambers from 150 mm to 225 mm, with both increasing in 25 mm increments from A to D.

The key variable among the four layouts was the spatial arrangement of the Reef cube[®] units, which simulated different reef configurations with consistent total volume but varying internal structure. In each layout, the 16 cubes of each type were arranged into a 4 x 4 x 4 stacked configuration (Figure 3).

OL1 was assembled in a simple stratified arrangement, with the void designs layered sequentially from base to top in the order A, B, C, and D - placing the smallest void spaces at the base and progressively larger ones above (Figure 3a). OL2 followed the inverse order (D, C, B, A), positioning the largest voids at the base and the smallest at the top (Figure 3b). OL3 retained the stratified layout but reordered the middle layers of OL1, resulting in an arrangement of A, D, B, and C from base to top (Figure 3c). OL4 employed a symmetrical, patterned arrangement, with designs interspersed throughout the height of the model to produce a more heterogeneous distribution, including vertical connections between some of the larger voids and the upper surface (Figure 3d). To simplify interpretation of the results the external environment was considered to be adjacent only to the upper surface of the ordered layouts.

Table 1. Design details related to the four types of Reef cube[®] units used to design the ordered simulated objects

Reef cube [®] type	Diagram	Total internal space	Passage diameter and	Chamber diameter and volume (mm)
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		volume (cm ³)	volume (mm)	
A		3600	75	150
B		4600	100	175
C		6600	125	200
D		8600	150	225

Figure 3 Ordered structural layouts a) Ordered Layout 1 (OL1), b) OL2, c) OL3 and d) OL4. OL1 and OL2 have symmetrically opposing layouts, with cubic units of decreasing internal space top to bottom in OL1 and units of increasing internal space top to bottom in OL2. OL3 has another reorganized layering with discrete horizontal layers, and OL4 has a complex symmetrical pattern of organization. Accessibility of the interstitial space was considered only from the upper horizontal face of the structures.

2.3 Nature-inclusive berm modelling

To showcase the use of accessible space analysis in eco-engineering practice, we applied the methodology to a hypothetical nature-inclusive design scenario: the pre-immersion assessment of a design's internal spatial structure as a predictor for success. We chose to investigate the use of void spaces integrated on a per unit basis, as a nature-inclusive design feature incorporated in to a berm-type structure, comparing a berm with integrated voids to a traditional design without integrated voids. Berms and similar structures, normally formed of piles of rocks, are commonly used in offshore energy industries for applications like cable protection, pipeline protection and scour protection.

We selected a hypothetical goal of enhancing juvenile fish populations, to frame the analysis. Two berm structures were 3D modelled using Blender software (Blender Foundation, 2023). The first model represented a conventional rock berm, constructed from polygonal meshes of rocks scaled to

follow a graded size distribution in accordance with established engineering design parameters. The average particle size was calibrated to match the 250 mm edge length of the Reef cube[®] units, while complying with industry standard specifications, under a grading designation with average mass and mass distribution of “category A light grading” LMA_{10/60} (British Standards Institution, 2002). The second model represented a proposed nature-inclusive berm design, incorporating the feasible nature-inclusive feature of internal void spaces (Glarou et al., 2020; Langhamer and Wilhelmsson, 2009; Wilson and Elliott, 2009). It was constructed from polygonal meshes of RC250 Reef cube[®] units, with an equal distribution (1:1:1:1) of the four internal void designs used in the ordered layouts (Table 1).

Both berms were modelled using a particle deposition simulation, similar to the procedure described by Sadchatheeswaran et al. (2019a). In brief, 49 m³ of material – either rocks (for the conventional berm) or Reef cube[®] units (for the nature-inclusive berm) – was animated in Blender to simulate a gravity-driven deployment process onto a flat seafloor surface. This approach approximated the formation of a berm deployed by a rock placement vessel.

At the end of the simulation, the resulting berm structures were consolidated into single unified models for subsequent analysis (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Simulated berm models formed by a) rocks or b) Reef cubes[®].

2.4 Measuring interstitial space metrics

To create visualisations of accessible space and calculate interstitial space metrics from the ordered and disordered reef layouts, an experimental software application was used – called “Hablab” (ARC Marine Ltd., 2025). The application utilises a novel numerical modelling routine that was created to measure accessible space metrics from 3D mesh models. The modelling routine functions by taking an STL file input and outputting interstitial space metrics, including V_{int} , AV and ARV for user defined access classes; along with a VTK point cloud file for visualising accessible space.

To measure the interstitial space metrics, the routine proceeds through six core steps: (1) file conversion, (2) spatial distance calculation, (3) accessibility calculation, (4) accessibility expansion, (5) final 3D structure creation and (6) species-specific structure creation.

1. During file conversion, once a 3D model is imported (Figure 5a), it is voxelated to a defined resolution, based on voxel edge length. Each voxel is then assigned a binary classification of either solid (0) or empty space (1) (Figure 5b).
2. Empty voxels are subsequently reclassified based on their Euclidean distance from the nearest solid voxel (Figure 5c).
3. The program then evaluates the connectivity of empty voxels that are both greater than or equal to accessing diameters and connected to at least one external surface opening (Figure 5d). The exterior of the structure is defined appropriately according to user input, with “open water” specified as above the model for samples cut from a larger structure, while standalone structures are assumed to be surrounded by “open water” on all sides.
4. Next, the algorithm spherically dilates these accessible voxels according to their magnitude, tagging voxels with the diameter of the largest sphere that could occupy their space and characterising the accessibility of interstitial space (Figure 5e).
5. V_{int} and AV are subsequently calculated after removing the external spaces. V_{int} is defined using the total number of voxels accessible to any species diameter. AV is defined using the total number of voxels tagged as accessible to diameters equal or above species diameters.
6. ARV is calculated by refining the structure to retain empty voxels accessible to the designated access class minimum diameter and removing those accessible to the access class maximum. An additional calculation is performed to more accurately represent real refugia by removing vestigial spaces which are only partially accessible to a sphere at the access class minimum. With each metric, the final value is obtained by multiplying the number of voxels by the voxel volume, equivalent to the voxel resolution cubed.

Figure 5. Conceptual diagram to illustrate the accessibility modelling routine from a) starting model, to b) file conversion, c) spatial distance calculation, d) accessibility calculation and e) accessibility expansion.

In this study, voxel resolution was set to 5 mm, which ensured high spatial resolution while optimising computational efficiency. Four access classes of ARV were calculated from the ordered layouts: ARV₁₈,

90, ARV_{58,290}, ARV_{98,490} and ARV_{138,690}. A minimum diameter of 18 mm was selected, as it is smaller than the narrowest internal constraints found in the ordered layouts and corresponds to the typical body size of plausible target species for enhancement, juvenile gadoid fishes, such as haddock, whiting, and cod –that have recently settled into benthic nursery grounds (Bastrikin et al., 2014; Waterman, 2001).

Recognizing that predator size is not always known (Bartholomew et al., 2000), we defined access class maxima using a general predator-prey size ratio commonly observed in marine fish predators, which has been established at approximately 5:1 (Scharf et al., 2000) and further confirmed by mesocosm studies on reef fish (Holmes and McCormick, 2009). For the berm structures, ARV was calculated using the same voxel resolution (5 mm), but considering ten access classes, ranging from ARV_{18,90mm} to ARV_{198,990mm} with classes increasing at 20 mm minima diameter intervals; and maxima thus increasing at 100 mm intervals, again following the 5:1 size ratio. This approach allowed for the assessment of how different design types may influence refuge accessibility and, by extension, species-level interactions, across a broad range of life history stages and taxa.

Visualisations of accessible space for this study were performed in Paraview software (Ahrens et al., 2005). Data analysis and visualisation was performed with R software, utilising the tidyverse set of packages (R Core Team, 2023; Wickham et al., 2019).

2.5 Measurement validation

To ensure the reliability of the novel measurement method, the routine's accuracy was first validated by comparing its V_{int} and AV outputs to geometrically calculated values, using the ordered layout models, where the known geometry allowed for exact calculation of these metrics (Supplementary Material). Geometric calculation of V_{int} was performed by summing the interstitial volume of all 64 individual Reef cube® units within the ordered layouts. AV was calculated by summing the interstitial volume of the units known to be accessible to a given diameter, within each different layout.

Modelled and expected AV values were compared using Bland-Altman analysis (Bland and Altman, 1986) to assess agreement and quantify any systematic bias between the two methods (Bland and Altman, 1999). Considering the model resolution, a mean difference of 10% or below was defined *a priori* as the threshold for good agreement (Giavarina, 2015). Pearson's correlation coefficient was also calculated to evaluate the strength of the linear relationship between modelled and expected results.

3.1 Ordered layout results

Validation analyses revealed a good agreement across all modelled and expected values for both V_{int} and AV (Supplementary document). The four ordered layouts exhibited different patterns of accessible space, due to different structural organisations in relation to the external environment adjacent to the upper face (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Accessible space in ordered layouts OL1 (a), OL2 (b), OL3 (c) and OL4 (d), coloured by accessing diameter. Accessibility was assessed considering the outer environment to be adjacent to the upper surface of the structures only (top down accessibility). Figure produced with 2 mm voxel resolution.

These variations in the accessibility of interstitial space led to differences in accessible volume and accessible refuge volume despite the layouts having the same total interstitial volume (0.378 m^3 ; Figure 7).

Accessible volume (AV) declined gradually from 0 to 75mm accessing diameters, before exhibiting step functions that varied between the four layouts (Figure 7a). Stepwise reductions in AV corresponded

to accessing diameters near or equal to the Reef cube® passage diameters (i.e., 75 mm, 100 mm, 125 mm and 150 mm; Table 1).

Ordered layout 2 exhibited the steepest decline in AV for accessing diameters above 75 mm, due to the presence of Reef cubes® with the smallest voids (Type A) in the top layer (Figure 6; Figure 7a). OL1 and OL4 exhibited similar AV profiles despite the different structure (Figure 6), with four negative steps in AV at accessing diameters at or near the Reef cube® passage diameters (Figure 7a). OL1 had a slightly higher AV at the largest accessing diameters (e.g. $AV_{140\text{ mm}} = 0.126\text{ m}^3$) compared to OL4 ($AV_{140\text{ mm}} = 0.103\text{ m}^3$).

OL3 displayed three distinct layers of accessible space, with the restructuring of layers restricting the maximum accessing diameter to 125 mm (Figure 6; Figure 7a).

OL2 showed substantially higher $ARV_{18-90\text{ mm}}$ values compared to the other layouts (0.049 m^3 , 0.050 m^3 and 0.048 m^3 , for OL1, OL3 and OL4 respectively; Figure 7b), because of the reduced AV at the class maximum (90 mm; Figure 7a). ARV values for the three larger access classes ($ARV_{58, 290\text{ mm}}$, $ARV_{98, 490\text{ mm}}$, $ARV_{138, 690\text{ mm}}$) aligned with the pattern of the AV values, due to the access class maxima being beyond the limit of accessing diameters (150 mm) for which any AV was found. The ARV values at these classes were therefore equal to the relative AV values for accessing diameters equal to the access class minima ($AV_{58\text{ mm}}$, $AV_{98\text{ mm}}$, $AV_{138\text{ mm}}$).

$ARV_{58, 290\text{ mm}}$ was similar between the four ordered layouts (0.335 m^3 , 0.344 m^3 , 0.340 m^3 and 0.340 m^3 for OL1, 2, 3 and 4 respectively). OL1 and OL4 exhibited the highest ARV values at the wider access classes: $ARV_{98, 490\text{ mm}}$ (0.219 m^3 and 0.223 m^3 respectively) and $ARV_{138, 690\text{ mm}}$ (0.115 m^3 and 0.097 m^3 respectively).

Figure 7. Interstitial space metrics for the ordered layouts: a) Accessible volume and b) a comparison of total interstitial volume (V_{int}) calculated via Euclidean geometry and by numerical modelling; and ARV for four access classes.

3.2 Nature-inclusive berm results

The rock and Reef cube[®] berm simulations produced digital models with similar external dimensions but with different accessible spaces, with differences notably present throughout the structures (Figure 9, Supplement 2). The rock reef reached a maximum height of 2.4 m, with a seafloor footprint of 76.0 m², occupying a total volume of 86.1 m³. The Reef cube[®] reef extended over 79.3 m² of seafloor,

reached 2.5 m in height, and had a total volume of 92.5 m³. Despite the similarities in physical dimensions and utilisation of the same material volume - as a sum of particle volumes - analysis of interstitial space revealed substantial differences between the reef designs. The Reef cube[®] berm exhibited 61.9 m³ of interstitial volume (V_{int}), accounting for 67% of the structure's total volume and exceeding that of the rock berm (37.4 m³, 44% of its total volume) by 66%.

Figure 8. Cross section of accessible space in (a) the Reef cube[®] berm and (b) rock berm. A human silhouette (height: 1.70 m) is included to provide a sense of scale.

The enhancement of total interstitial volume by the Reef cubes[®] was accompanied by a higher accessible volume across a range of accessing diameters, especially for accessing diameters below 150 mm (average increase of $AV_{<150\text{ mm}} = 25.9\text{ m}^3 \pm \text{s.d. } 6.3\text{ m}^3$; Figure 9a). The magnitude of differences between the two layouts gradually increased with accessing diameter, peaking at 95 mm, where the Reef cube[®] berm provided 34.3 m^3 more $AV_{95\text{ mm}}$ compared to the rock berm. Beyond this point, while absolute differences declined, the relative difference (percentage increase from rock to Reef cube[®]) continued to rise, reaching a maximum at 120 mm accessing diameter, where the Reef cube[®] structure exhibited 29.8 m^3 more AV, corresponding to a 370% increase. The difference between the two designs dropped drastically at 150 mm but there remained at least 1.0 m^3 more AV for the Reef cube[®] berm up to accessing diameters of 200 mm.

ARV values across all 10 access classes were on average 172% higher in the Reef cube[®] berm than the rock berm, with the highest ARV for both structures at $ARV_{38,190\text{ mm}}$ (Figure 9b). The pattern of differences in ARV between the two structures was similar to AV but with a difference at the lowest access class ($ARV_{18,90\text{ mm}}$). $ARV_{18,90\text{ mm}}$ in the Reef cube berm (8.1 m^3) was lower compared to the rock berm (17.6 m^3), due to higher $AV_{90\text{ mm}}$ for the classes' maximum. ARV values were higher in the Reef cube[®] berm for the remaining nine access classes. The greatest differences were in the six access classes from $ARV_{38,190\text{ mm}}$ through $ARV_{138,690\text{ mm}}$ with increases ranging from 12.9 m^3 ($ARV_{138,690\text{ mm}}$) to 31.9 m^3 ($ARV_{98,490\text{ mm}}$). Differences in the largest three classes were of lower magnitude, with diminishing increases compared to the rock, from an increase of 1.2 m^3 ($ARV_{158,790\text{ mm}}$), to an increase of 0.5 m^3 ($ARV_{198,990\text{ mm}}$).

Figure 9. (a) AV and (b) ARV values for the modelled berm structures

4 DISCUSSION

4.1 Interpretation of results

4.1.1 Ordered layouts

Our results proved accessible space metrics to be volume-independent in their description of interstitial space. The four ordered layouts, despite being composed of the same Reef cube[®] units, and containing the same total interstitial volume, displayed different profiles of accessible space. Based on the arrangement of the different sized Reef cubes[®] in relation to the upper face - designated as

adjacent to the external environment - the different designs produced different quantities of AV and ARV across accessing diameters and access classes respectively. Whilst V_{int} remained constant, supported through geometric validation, the accessibility metrics and visualisation of accessible space successfully distinguished between the different spatial arrangements.

The ordered layout results confirmed the importance of considering the layout of interstitial spaces relative to the external environment during nature-inclusive design of void features as a trait that affects structural complexity (Tokeshi and Arakaki, 2012). Resulting differences in AV and ARV, driven by the structural differences, suggest that the layout designs could function differently for ecological communities exposed to the structures, as observed by Taira et al. (2024) on the effects of altering interstitial space organisation while maintaining total volume. For example, ordered layout 2 - which included the smallest voids adjacent to the exterior environment - had an internal space network that was inaccessible to any species over the smallest 75 mm passage size. Ordered layout 1 on the other hand, by having the reverse design, with the largest units at the top, provided interstitial space that could be accessed by a wider size range of species, including larger species up to 150 mm in diameter, in the upper levels of the structure. Depending on the design goals, one of these layouts could prove more suitable than the other. If targeting smaller lifeforms and creating refugia from larger predators then OL2 might be more suitable, whereas if targeting larger organisms or a range of lifeforms then OL1 might be more suitable. The difference in these two designs also highlights the importance of considering the entire curve of AV, and the additionality provided by the ARV metric. Whilst both structures had identical accessible volume for species up to 75 mm, the feasible amount of refugia for prey species of 18 mm was significantly higher in OL2, considering the exclusion of hypothetical predatory species of 90 mm diameter. As shown in the present study, AV and ARV are complimentary and closely related but differ based on interstitial arrangement, yielding valuable insight into the spatial architecture of structured habitats.

AV and ARV metrics also revealed similarities between designs that appeared visually dissimilar (e.g., OL1 and OL4) yet ultimately defined nearly identical profiles of accessible space. This suggests that the metrics proposed here are capable of overcoming subjective visual interpretation, which may often be misleading or fail to reflect actual structural performance.

4.1.2 *Nature-inclusive berm design*

The Reef cube® berm had a considerably larger and more interconnected network of interstitial space compared to the traditional rock berm. This was due to the 3,128 Reef cubes®, each providing integral refuge spaces that remained accessible to a wide array of species throughout the entire structure

(Figure 9 and Supplementary Information). In this way, a greater proportion of this space was accessible to a broader range of organism sizes, particularly those up to 150 mm in diameter, resulting in a substantially higher provision of refugia for prey species between 38 mm and 150 mm in size.

The rock berm on the other hand had a smaller network of interstitial volume, that was more tightly shaped by the graded design, resulting in a lower accessibility. In the same way that OL2 might restrict access to organisms of larger diameters, increasing ARV values for smaller access classes, the interlocking arrangement in the traditional rock berm strongly limited the accessibility at higher ARV access classes.

The results suggest that the Reef cube® berm could have a high likelihood of success in achieving the designated design goal of enhancing juvenile fish populations, because of the considerable uplift in accessible interstitial space and refuge volume across a greater range of juvenile species and life stages. In a theoretical nature-inclusive design scenario, this design could be a promising candidate to take forward for a real-world study.

The ARV and AV metrics were both able to capture the different internal structure driven by both the rigid internal void features provided in the Reef cube® unit design and the tighter interlocking of rocks together in the graded design. AV results showed a declining pattern that somewhat corresponded to the passage design diameter of the Reef cubes® though not as starkly as in the ordered layouts, likely due to the complex disordered organization of the units. The capability of AV to detect such trends is particularly important in the context of nature-inclusive design, as it allows the evaluation of potential design improvements prior to deployment. In this case, AV showed how modifications to the void space on the unit scale can significantly influence interstitial space accessibility across large portions of complex, disordered reef systems such as the Reef cube® berm.

4.2 Practical application

Structural complexity has been shown to be a strong predictor of marine community structure, functions and dynamics (Ferrari et al., 2018; Urbina-Barreto et al., 2022), but only when assessed at spatial scales that are ecologically relevant to the body size of the organisms involved (Pygas et al., 2020). While considerable attention has been given to external complexity, which is relatively easy to characterise through external surveys of a structure, including visual estimation (Consoli et al., 2018), special devices (Wilding et al., 2007), or advanced photogrammetry (Urbina-Barreto et al., 2021); addressing internal or interstitial complexity presents a far greater methodological challenge. The network of tunnels and cavities that connect within a structured habitat in a labyrinth-like fashion has been observed to significantly affect marine community dynamics (Hendy et al., 2014), although to

date, such effects have been observed for artificial structures predominantly in controlled experimental contexts (Taira et al., 2024). Extending such investigations retrospectively (Sadchatheeswaran et al., 2019b), or applying them to planned structures, is currently constrained by the lack of suitable tools. This gap hampers our ability to understand species–habitat relationships in structurally complex habitats and limits the application of these concepts to nature-positive approaches, such as the nature-inclusive design of marine infrastructure (Pardo et al., 2023). The development of testable goals and quantitative habitat metrics as predictors of ecological outcomes are key procedural steps in good-practice nature-inclusive design (British Standards Institution, 2025), and the lack of appropriate habitat metrics may therefore constrain the effective implementation of such design approaches.

Accessible space analysis is an innovative approach capable of characterising the internal complexity of marine hard substrates from a new perspective based on the accessibility of interstitial spaces to organisms of specific body sizes. Unlike many existing metrics, this method is unconfounded by other geometrical properties of the structure, which is a common limitation of many existing metrics (Loke et al., 2019). Accessible Volume (AV) and its derivative Accessible Refuge Volume (ARV) are proposed here as versatile metrics applicable across contexts, which may help explain predator-prey dynamics while accounting for other spatial covariates. In doing so, accessible space analysis underscores the crucial, yet often overlooked role that spatial arrangement plays in contributing to habitat complexity and shaping community structure (Loke and Chisholm, 2022; Tokeshi and Arakaki, 2012).

4.3 Integration With Literature

4.3.1 *Nature-inclusive design and artificial reef research*

Although the predictive power of ARV remains to be validated through field applications, our pre-immersion simulations suggest that a generalised Reef cube® berm is expected to perform better than a conventional rock-based structure by providing a greater availability of internal refugia. This expectation aligns with nature-inclusive design recommendations, which advocate the deployment of artificial reef units containing void spaces to enhance benthic fish populations around structures traditionally constructed from graded rock, such as offshore wind farm scour protection (Lengkeek et al., 2017; Wilson and Elliott, 2009), and are supported by case studies showing positive effects in incorporating diverse void features into artificial reef designs (Charbonnel, 2002; Sherman et al., 2002; Taira et al., 2024). The most comparable case study is the Loch Linhe artificial reef, which compared berm-like reef modules, created with solid blocks – representing low complexity – and hollow blocks – representing high complexity (Sayer and Wilding, 2002). Here, multiple positive effects of the

inclusion of voids in the complex reef were found compared to the simple reef, including enhanced fish abundance (Hunter and Sayer, 2009) and secondary production (Rouse et al., 2020).

The distinction between AV and ARV metrics is important for nature-inclusive and artificial reef design practices, because the upper size limit of refugia is important in driving community dynamics in artificial habitats. Research has shown that a single large void may be less effective than multiple smaller, more diverse voids in promoting species richness and ecological performance (Charbonnel, 2002; Hylkema et al., 2020; Sherman et al., 2002; Taira et al., 2024). From a metric perspective, ARV complements AV by providing an indication of the amount of refuge space that is usable by organisms of different sizes, thus offering a better proxy for ecological value, particularly in relation to juvenile fish enhancement. This insight is closely linked to the ecology of refugia in hard substrate habitats, where predation is a known driver of species diversity, abundance, and productivity (Eklund, 1997; Langhamer, 2012).

Fish actively seek and utilise refugia in response to the presence of predators (Magellan, 2020), and the creation of permanent refugia in reef habitats that exclude predators has positive effects on the abundance and resulting diversity of reef fishes (Caley and St John, 1996). Furthermore, fish species can exhibit enhanced abundance with increased refuge availability, that is separate from any reduction in predation, likely due to strong habitat preferences (Steele, 1999). The degree to which a particular species will utilise hard substrate refugia and exhibit a benefit from the introduction and effective design of artificial substrata, will therefore vary based on the species' lifestyle and ecology (Fabi et al., 2015), as well as the interaction between its morphology and the interstitial spaces architecture.

4.3.2 Gaps and future perspectives

Gaps in this study predominantly revolve around two areas, firstly the requirement for real world ecological validation and secondly the exclusion of alternative plausible analysis settings and metrics to focus the study. Investigations in the future could aim to address these gaps.

The greatest gap to be overcome is the requirement for ecological investigation in real world settings into the effects of variations in accessibility metrics. As ecological data remains to be integrated with accessible space analysis, quantitative ecological predictions remain to be developed and validated from field studies.

Our study includes models of hypothetical real world berm structures, at time zero following construction. This doesn't include any variations due to feasible environmental effects like sediment deposition, or the growth of biota on the surfaces of structures, which could subsequently alter the interstitial space and its accessibility, depending on the environmental conditions in the locality of

deployment. Modelling methods could be developed utilising data from structures through time to chart the alterations in spatial geometry.

We assessed refugia generalistically for juvenile fishes, whereby access classes for ARV calculations were designated with maxima corresponding to predators five times the diameter of prey. Different species and life history stages will likely exhibit different habitat preferences and refugia requirements, for different functions, thus careful designation of access classes should be performed to suit different species and functional habitat queries. For example, some invertebrates like mussels, tend to favour smaller refugia that more closely match their body diameter (Bertolini et al., 2018). In a scenario where the designer is targeting greater survivorship of such species then the access classes should be made narrower for pre-immersion assessment of the structure.

The scope of our metrics' calculations covered the entirety of the structural designs but we propose that AV and ARV can be flexible to the required scenario. In this instance - comparing habitats of known limits and dimensions - we deemed quantification over total habitat structures to be a good approach.

Both metrics could be quantified alternatively, based on subsamples of a larger habitat; standardised to a unit of volume, or footprint area; or standardised against total interstitial volume to create a dimensionless measurement. Utilisation of a dimensionless measurement by standardising the metrics against the total interstitial volume could be valuable for making results comparable across studies and habitat types (Loke and Chisholm, 2022).

Finally, there is an additional consideration in the limits of the accessibility metrics AV and ARV proposed here. Depth, position and the pattern of interconnectedness of the accessible spaces within the structure are not revealed with these metrics alone as shown in the ordered layout results when comparing OL1 and OL4 and could provide complimentary insights as additional novel metrics.

5 CONCLUSION

Disentangling the influence of structural complexity on biological communities and their dynamics remains a significant challenge. However, accessible space analysis represents a novel approach to quantifying and visualising interstitial space that could help to clarify the role of interstitial space in shaping community composition. By incorporating a consideration of accessibility, AV and ARV metrics help to illustrate both the form and function of structured habitats. In this demonstrative article we have shown that AV and ARV are more responsive to modifications in the design of void space geometry in complex structured habitats, than the established metric V_{Int} . By testing a conceptual nature-inclusive design, we showed that AV and ARV are uplifted via the integration of artificial reef void design features. Through sensitivity to spatial configurations and by incorporating access classes,

ARV particularly has a distinctive potential to act as a predictive variable for species dynamics, especially predation, and by extension, community structure. In providing such insights, analysis of accessible space can inform the design of evidence-based, nature-inclusive structures aligned with specific ecological objectives.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

All authors are employed by ARC Marine Ltd., an eco-engineering company involved in nature-inclusive design and the production of structures such as the Reef cubes® modelled in this study. As such, the company may potentially benefit from the scientific validation and positive reception of its methods and products.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The resources supporting the findings of this study are openly available via Zenodo.

- **Dataset:** Hickling, S. et al. (2025). Analytical data for "Habitat accessibility in the design of nature-inclusive void features in marine structures" [Dataset]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17130947>
- **Software:** ARC Marine Ltd. (2025). Hablab program: research version [Software]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17151439>. Available at <https://github.com/Kyle-ARCMarine/hablab>

Model validation checks are available in the supplementary material provided along with this paper.

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